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METAL DELM.

UNPUBLISHED QUADRANTES FROM THE NATIONAL MUSEUM IN BELGRADE AND THE FAJFRIĆ COLLECTION

Abstract: This paper presents seven previously unpublished Roman nummi metallorum - quadrantes bearing reference to the metalla of Delmatia -, as well as two anonymous quadrantes. The coins originate from two private collections: the Kovačević collection which today is part of the Numismatic Collection of the National Museum in Belgrade, and the collection of Petar Fajfrić from Šabac. The five nummi metallorum which are now in the Fajfrić collection were all found on the territory of Banovo Polje (commune of Bogatić) in Serbia.

Keywords: metalla Delmatiae, nummi metallorum, anonymous quadrantes, Kovačević collection, Banovo Polje

The so-called *nummi metallorum* ("coins of the mines")¹ are a peculiar class of small bronze coins bearing reference to various mining districts in the Danube and Balkan provinces of the Roman Empire. They were struck from the reign of Trajan (AD 98-117) down to the reign of Antoninus Pius (AD 138-161). Eight years ago, the first systematic treatment of these *semisses* and *quadrantes* - which had been attracting the attention of scholars for several centuries - was published, and all the known types and varieties were finally presented in a citable catalogue.² However, as research on Roman

¹ The authors would like to thank the curator of the Numismatic Collection of the National Museum in Belgrade, Bojana Borić-Brešković, and Slavoljub Petrović of the National Museum in Šabac for granting access to the coins published in this article and for providing invaluable information. Special gratitude goes to Mr Petar Fajfrić who has kindly permitted the publication of coins from his private collection. The authors are also indebted to Nebojša Borić from the Institute of Archaeology in Belgrade, who supplied the high-quality images.

² Woytek 2004a; Woytek 2004b.

mining in general progresses,³ more numismatic work on several aspects of the subject is needed. For example, a major problem is posed by the fact that most of the coins of the mines known today came to light through coin trade, and any reliable information on their provenance is lost. Hence, the circulation patterns of the different types of *nummi metallorum* are still not completely clear. The present authors strive to remedy this situation in the course of their joint research on the Roman coins of the mines. As a first step, in this paper seven hitherto unpublished *nummi metallorum* and two anonymous *quadrantes* from two Serbian collections are presented.

This selection of the material requires some comment. These two classes of coinage have been grouped together in some numismatic publications.⁴ Despite the fact that the anonymous *semisses* and *quadrantes*⁵ do not bear reference to mines in their legends – they are all signed just with the letters SC – and that there is only the odd typological point of contact between the two groups,⁶ the specific purpose and *raison d'être* of *nummi metallorum* and anonymous bronze coins has sometimes been seen as related. Although the two types of coinage are indeed occasionally found in the same contexts, this is a highly problematic assumption, as has already been pointed out elsewhere,⁷ and it is *a priori* not endorsed by the present authors. Both classes of coinage represent small change of the imperial denominational system, but further common features between the two still remain to be proven. Thus, the decision to publish coins from both classes together in this article has been made for the sole purpose of bringing as many as possible otherwise unpublished coins of a similar date to the wider numismatic public. In keeping with the different contexts from which the coins originate, the material will be presented here according to its present collection affiliation.

I. National Museum Belgrade, the Kovačević Collection

Ljubomir Kovačević (1848–1918) was a historian, university professor and an education minister in the government of the Kingdom of Serbia.⁸ As an academic he was one of the first in his homeland to recognize the importance of the ‘source disciplines’ such as numismatics for historical research, and he was one of the earlier studious numismatists and scholarly coin collectors in the Central Balkans. His main area of interest was the coinage of the Serbian Medieval state, which forms the core

³ See e.g. Hirt 2010; Mladenović in press, with review of earlier scholarship.

⁴ See, for example, Simić and Vasić 1977, esp. 52–54, as well as the bibliographical indications given by Weigel 1998, 17, note 62.

⁵ The best modern treatment is by van Heesch 1979, Hoofdstuk IV: De anonieme munten, 199–254 (who convincingly dates these anonymous coins to the reign of Antoninus Pius).

⁶ E.g. RIC II, Anonymous Quadrantes 12 (obv. bust of Roma, rev. Aequitas standing left) and 19 (obv. bust of Mars, rev. cuirass), to be compared with the *nummi metallorum* Woytek 2004a, nos VI, VII and XII.

⁷ See Weigel 1998, 18; Woytek 2004a, 50, note 90.

⁸ Ćirković and Mihaljčić 1997, 440–441.

of his 3000-specimen strong collection. Ancient coins were included into his collection only sporadically, without a clear focus. Unfortunately, like many collectors of his day, Kovačević did not keep detailed records on the origin of the pieces that came into his possession, so the provenance of his coins is hard to determine with any degree of certainty. This is also true of the coins that are published here. In any case, the majority of his collection doubtless came from the territory of late 19th century Serbia,⁹ since the material he was mainly interested in obtaining – Serbian medieval coinage – is predominantly found in this region. The haphazard nature of Kovačević's classical coin collection might suggest that the ancient coins were acquired more or less by chance alongside medieval pieces that were his main focus, but this remains a speculation. After Kovačević's death, the integrity of his coin collection was maintained and it was bequested to the National Museum in Belgrade, in the possession of which it remains as a distinct collection.

Four coins selected for publication from the collection at this point are the following:¹⁰

Nummi metallorum

1.

Quadrans

Obv. Bust of Diana to the right, wearing stephane, with chignon at the back of the neck and quiver over the shoulder. Border of dots.

Rev. ME[TAL DEL]M

Stag standing left. Border of dots.

weight 2.34g; maximum diameter 13.8mm; die axis 7h

Inv. no. NMBg K 768

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

2.

Quadrans

As no. 1 above; reverse legend METAL DELM

weight 2.95g; maximum diameter 16.7mm; die axis 7h

Inv. no. NMBg K 769

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

⁹ Which unlike the present-day state of Serbia extended only south of the Sava and the Danube, up to but excluding South Serbia and Kosovo.

¹⁰ Within separate classes of coinage the organization of this catalogue follows the museum's inventory numbers.

Anonymous quadrantes

3.

Quadrans

Obv. Helmeted and cuirassed bust of bearded Mars to the right. [Border of dots.]

Rev. S-C

Cuirass. [Border of dots.]

weight 2.50g; maximum diameter 15.3mm; die axis 1h

Inv. no. NMBg K 513

References: van Heesch 1979, no. 2a; RIC Anonymous quadrantes no. 19

4.

Quadrans

Obv. Winged griffon to the right [touching wheel with a front paw]. Border of dots

Rev. S-C

Tripod. Border of dots.

weight 2.06g; maximum diameter 15.5mm; die axis 3h

Inv. no. NMBg K 783

References: van Heesch 1979, no. 24; RIC Anonymous quadrantes no. 27

II. The Fajfrić Collection

The five *nummi metallorum* from the collection of Petar Fajfrić have a secure provenance: according to information provided by the collector, they all come from the site Duge Njive, on the territory of the village Banovo Polje (commune of Bogatić) in western Serbia (Figure 1). All of the coins were individual chance finds made over the period of several years, from 2004 to 2010. The *nummi metallorum* from this collection are currently on temporary deposit at the National Museum Šabac. Duge Njive, where they were found, is located on a slope, nestled above the confluence of the stream Batar into the Zasavica. Its position is very favourable as it remains dry even when high waters submerge the surrounding ground. Today it is intensively farmed, and it is through agricultural activities that archaeological material comes to light. The site was never investigated properly, but over the years it has yielded a considerable amount of archaeological finds, including coins of primarily 2nd and 3rd century AD date.¹¹ Finds and reported remains of structures seem to indicate the existence of a small rural settlement at this location, possibly a *villa rustica*. Many farming villas have been recorded in this fertile agricultural landscape of Mačva, with perhaps

¹¹ Petrović 2010, 112. For a detailed description of the site and an overview of existing literature see Vojvoda and Petrović 2011.

four more sites of this type within the territory of Banovo Polje itself.¹² The village is located in the region of the supposed south Pannonian mining district centred around Mt Cer (50 km to the south),¹³ of which archaeologically nothing is known. The wider area is a border region between three Roman provinces: Moesia Superior, Dalmatia and Pannonia.

Figure 1. Banovo Polje and its surroundings (after the Topographic Map of the Military Geographical Institute, Belgrade, sector 427-2-2, Bijeljina 2-2 (Banovo Polje); scale: 1: 25,000)

*Nummi metallorum*¹⁴

5. *Quadrans*

Obv. Bust of Diana to the right, wearing stephane, with chignon at the back of the neck and quiver over the shoulder. Border of dots.

Rev. METAL DELM
Stag standing left. Border of dots.

weight 2.87g; maximum diameter 15.2mm; die axis 6h

National Museum Šabac, temporary deposit, inv. no. "Priv. Coll. 1"

¹² Vasić 1985, 126, 138 nos. 84, 96; Vasiljević 1996, 36-37, nos. 44, 56; Vojvoda and Petrović 2011, 284-285.

¹³ Dušanić 2004, 251.

¹⁴ Again, this catalogue is organized according to the inventory numbers of the museum where they are currently kept.

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

6.

Quadrans

As no. 5 above; reverse legend METAL [DELM]

weight 2.00g; maximum diameter 12.7mm; die axis 7h

National Museum Šabac, temporary deposit, inv. no. "Priv. Coll. 2"

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

7.

Quadrans

As no. 5 above; reverse legend METAL DELM

weight 1.60g; maximum diameter 13mm; die axis 7h

National Museum Šabac, temporary deposit, inv. no. "Priv. Coll. 3"

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

8.

Quadrans

As no. 5 above; reverse legend METAL DE[LM]

weight 1.57g; maximum diameter 14mm; die axis 6h

National Museum Šabac, temporary deposit, inv. no. "Priv. Coll. 4"

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

9.

Quadrans

As no. 5 above; reverse legend [METAL DE]LM

weight 2.30g; flan of irregular shape, maximum diameter 14-16.1mm; die axis 2h

National Museum Šabac, temporary deposit, inv. no. "Priv. Coll. 5"

References: Woytek 2004a, type XIII (with illustration XIII/2 on p. 67); van Heesch 1979, no. 24b; RIC Hadrian no. 1013; BMC Hadrian no. 1854

The *metalla* of the Roman province of *Delmatia* are mentioned on two different, chronologically separate groups of bronze coins. Rare *semisses* and *quadrantes* minted under Trajan in AD 112-114 bear the emperor's portrait and the reverse legend METALLI VLPIANI DELM, which accompanies a female figure holding a balance and a *cornucopiae*.¹⁵ The type of *nummi metallorum* published here, from the

¹⁵ Woytek 2004a, nos. 6f.; see also Woytek 2010, nos. 613-614.

Kovačević and Fajfrić collections, belongs to the second group, which lacks an imperial portrait. This group, convincingly dated to the reign of Antoninus Pius (AD 138–161) by Johan van Heesch,¹⁶ comprises, beside the described *quadrantes* with Diana and her stag, also *semisses* depicting Mars and a cuirass.¹⁷ These *semisses* differ from the “anonymous” *semisses* and *quadrantes* with the same images¹⁸ only in their reverse legend, which is METAL DELM (instead of SC). It is immediately evident that the coin types of obverse and reverse of the anonymous METAL DELM-bronzes are designed to match. The choice of the deities Diana and Mars, on the other hand, must be seen in the context of anonymous coins of the mines of the same period featuring the legends METAL AVRELIANIS and METAL PANNONICIS, on the obverses of which Apollo/Sol is depicted.¹⁹ All of these series were obviously designed as a set by some central authority. Taken together, these anonymous *nummi metallorum* present the deities to whom the metals gold (Apollo/Sol), silver (Diana/Luna) and iron (Mars) were attributed, according to ancient astrological belief.²⁰ Consequently, the assumption that gold, silver and iron were mined in the districts named on the reverses of the coins seems to suggest itself. In the case of the METAL DELM coins the choice of Diana and Mars is in keeping with the archaeological and epigraphic evidence we possess for mining in Delmatia: silver and iron were indeed the most important products from mines in this region.²¹ It should be noted, though, that an association between Apollo/Sol on the METAL AVRELIANIS and METAL PANNONICIS coins and gold mining in Pannonia is purely hypothetical, as we have no independent confirmation that gold was indeed a significant product of this mining district.²²

Regarding the material published here, two points of importance should be highlighted. First, as far as we know, the METAL DELM *quadrantes* from the Fajfrić collection are the only coins of this type for which a secure provenance can be given to date.²³ In other cases, the evidence is inconclusive. For example, two *quadrantes* with Diana/stag in the Numismatic Collection of the National Museum in Belgrade belong to the Weifert collection,²⁴ which was formed in Serbia mainly from locally sourced material.²⁵ For single specimens, the origin is, however, not verifiable. Hence, for the coins of the mines from the Weifert collection the problems are essentially

¹⁶ See van Heesch 1979, 180f.

¹⁷ RIC Hadrian 1014; BMC Hadrian 1856; van Heesch 1979, no. 23; Woytek 2004a, no. XII.

¹⁸ See, e.g. the *quadrans* published here as no. 3.

¹⁹ Woytek 2004a, nos VIII–XI.

²⁰ Hirt 2010, 65; Woytek 2004a, 44 (with further references).

²¹ See, for example, the “proc(urator) argentariarum Pannoniarum et Delmatarum” (ILS 1421) or the “[procurator] arg(entariarum) Delmatica[rum]” (AE 1948, no. 243); Hirt 2010, 63; Mladenović in press; Škegro 2000.

²² Dušanić 2004, 251, see especially footnote 24 for the circular nature of this argument.

²³ It may be noted here in passing that one METAL DELM *semis* (Woytek 2004a, type XII) was part of a Roman coin hoard unearthed in Regensburg in Germany: see Woytek 2004a, 54 (with note 112a).

²⁴ Elmer 1929, 50, nos. 847–848 = Simić and Vasić 1977, 58, nos. 20–21.

²⁵ On this point, see Elmer 1929, IV.

comparable to the ones we have to face for the pieces from the Kovačević collection published above: there is no hard and fast geographic evidence for their provenance.

Second, it must be stressed that the *quadrantes* of the METAL DELM type come in two different typological varieties, as already observed by van Heesch and one of the authors of this contribution.²⁶ While on the majority of specimens Diana wears a stephane and has a chignon at the back of her neck, she is sometimes depicted without a stephane and with a different, melon-shaped hairstyle (with a bun at the top): see for example Figure 2.²⁷ Stylistically, the coins of the latter type tend to be fine and largely uniform, while the larger group featuring Diana with a stephane is different and rather heterogeneous, in terms of style. Many of these pieces are quite crude, and a dividing line between “regular” and “imitative” pieces is not always easy to draw within this group. These stylistic observations tie in well with the metrology: the coins featuring the bust of Diana with a stephane are often lighter and sometimes weigh only around 1.5 grammes.

Figure 2. BMC Hadrian 1855 (image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

The seven METAL DELM *quadrantes* published in this article belong exclusively to the variety with stephane. Especially some of the coins from Duge Njive in the Fajfrić collection (our nos. 6–9) are typical examples of the pieces of a lesser style from this group. The fact that no. 9 is struck on an irregular flan adds to the picture; it is obvious that these coins were produced quite carelessly, both in terms of die engraving and of striking. It is to be hoped that more material will become available for study in the near future, so that a better understanding of the *nummi metallorum* of the METAL DELM-group can be developed. The cooperation of private collectors like Petar Fajfrić, who are willing to share information on unpublished numismatic material from local contexts in their possession, may well provide us with crucial pieces of evidence in the years to come.

²⁶ van Heesch 1979, 197; Woytek 2004a, 42.

²⁷ We illustrate a specimen kept at the British Museum, BMC Hadrian 1855 (struck on a thick flan of 3.86g, 6h); see also, for this hairstyle, e.g. MMAG FPL 167 (April 1957), 39 (illustrated in Woytek 2004a, 67, no. XIII/1), ANS 1954.20.1 (2.32g, 12h) and a specimen in an Austrian private collection (2.63g, 6h). For van Heesch 1979, 180, the occurrence of these two hairstyles was an additional argument to date the METAL DELM coins to the reign of Antoninus Pius, since he compared them to hairstyles in evidence on coins struck for Faustina II. This point, however, requires further research.

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Abbreviations:

AE	<i>L'Année épigraphique</i>
ANS	American Numismatic Society
BMC	H. Mattingly, <i>Coins of the Roman Empire in the British Museum</i> . Vol. 3: Nerva to Hadrian, London 1936 (reprinted with revisions 1976).
ILS	<i>Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae</i> I-III (Ed. H. Dessau. Berlin 1892-1916).
MMAG FPL	Münzen & Medaillen AG, Basel, Fixed Price List
RIC	H. Mattingly, E. A. Sydenham, <i>The Roman Imperial Coinage</i> . Vol. 2: Vespasian to Hadrian, London 1926 (reprinted 1989).

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METAL DELM.
НЕПУБЛИКОВАНИ КВАДРАНСИ ИЗ НАРОДНОГ МУЗЕЈА У БЕОГРАДУ
И ЗБИРКЕ ФАЈФРИЋ

РЕЗИМЕ

У овом раду аутори презентују седам до сада необјављених примерака рудничког новца (*nummi metallorum*), као и два анонимна квадранса. Сви примерци рудничког новца су квадранси са легендом *metal. Delm.* и припадају истом типу са Дијаном на аверсу и јеленом на реверсу. Новац потиче из две привате колекције: збирке Ковачевић, која данас чини саставни део нумизматичког фонда Народног музеја у Београду, и приватне збирке Петра Фајфрића из Шапца. Пет *nummi metallorum* који потичу из збирке Фајфрић су сви нађени на територији села Баново Поље (општина Богатић, Србија), што овом материјалу даје посебан значај чинећи их јединим примерцима тога типа за које се поуздано зна место налаза.

Кључне речи: *metalla Dalmatiae*, *nummi metallorum*, руднички новац, анонимни квадранси, збирка Ковачевић, Баново Поље

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